

3DOS Error Analysis and 3D Ultrasound Scanning Application Proposal

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Abstract

The widespread application of 3D point cloud analysis has garnered significant research interest, particularly regarding the handling of out-of-distribution (OOD) data, which is crucial for real-world safety-demanding applications. To enhance neural network robustness, this report investigates mechanisms based on error analysis. Specifically, we reproduce key results from 3DOS [2] and conduct a statistical analysis to understand the underlying causes of underconfidence and overconfidence, which contribute to performance degradation. We compare various methods across different families and backbones. Additionally, we propose a real-world application for 3D Semantic Novelty Detection. The code for this study is available at [here](#).

1. Introduction

The Open Set problem is of paramount importance in real world applications. 3DOS follows the hypothesis that a better accuracy might be correlated with a better distinction between In Distribution and Out of Distribution observations, given a certain model. Even if Semantic Novelty is a subset of the Out of Distribution case, so this doesn't entail the former, it might be a good enough proxy for it and evidence in the 3DOS experiments is coherent with it. We tried to replicate those results, then we focused on a qualitative perspective, to guide follow up work. Aligned with the increasing adoption of Transfer Learning techniques and Foundation models, we tried to leverage the representation power of OpenShape to handle the OOD Detection subtask of our Open Set task.

2. Related Works

3D image machine learning tasks showed that convolutional layer were a powerful yet perfectible architecture. It's application to 3D tasks, both through voxelization and views didn't perform as well as native 2D problems. But the theory behind convolutional layers mechanisms was hiding a broader and more powerful concept. As Bronstein et al. [3] showed in the emerging topic of Geometric Deep Learning, 2D convolution is nothing more than an operation that encodes the underlying manifold that we assume exists within images. Alternative options have been emerging and 3D manifolds modules able to natively handle point clouds have been born. Firstly PointNet [8], [9] showed how shared MLP blocks and other permutationally invariant operators like Pooling were effectively able to act as set operators. Then more theoretically based ones like DGCNN [14]

proposed more fine grained and modular manifold learning operators. Still, due to the above difficulties and more complex data collection processes, 3D datasets and benchmarks are way less than their 2D counterpart; and so they are benchmarks. 3DOS [2] tries to help in this context, proposing a benchmark for multiple models, trained with multiple losses, tested for different tasks one of them being OOD detection nevertheless performed with different approaches, lastly treating both synthetic, real and synthetic to real cases. We tried to replicate 3DOS results and to further investigate when the analyzed models failed.

2.1. Datasets

2.1.1 ModelNet40

ModelNet40 [15] is a widely used benchmark dataset in 3D shape classification and retrieval tasks. It contains 12,311 3D models divided into 40 object categories, such as airplanes, cars, chairs, and tables. Each category includes a variety of objects, providing a comprehensive set for training and evaluating machine learning models involving point clouds, voxel grids, and views. The dataset has been extensively used to validate the performance of various 3D deep learning algorithms.

Figure 1. samples from ModelNet40

2.1.2 ScanObjectNN

ScanObjectNN [13], unlike synthetic datasets like ModelNet40, consists of 2,902 objects categorized into 15 classes, derived from real indoor scene scans. This dataset includes noise, occlusions, and other imperfections typical of real-world scanning, providing a more challenging and realistic benchmark for evaluating the robustness and generalization ability of 3D object recognition models. It's of high importance for the development of algorithms that can handle practical issues encountered in real-world 3D data. Notice, in Figure 2, that the samples from ScanObjectNN are more practically challenging due to

complex background (points in lighter color), missing parts, and deformations.

Figure 2. samples from ScanObjectNN

2.1.3 Discriminative

Discriminative methods are a class of machine learning algorithms designed to model the decision boundary between different classes directly. Instead of modeling the underlying distribution of the data for each class, discriminative methods focus on learning the relationships and patterns that distinguish one class from another. This is typically achieved by training the model to maximize the probability of the correct class label given the input data.

2.1.4 MSP

Maximum Softmax Probability (MSP) is a commonly used method for evaluating the confidence of predictions made by a neural network. In a classification setting, the network outputs a probability distribution across all possible classes for a given input. MSP is defined as the maximum value in this probability distribution, representing the model’s confidence in its most likely prediction. MSP is particularly useful in tasks such as out-of-distribution detection, where it helps identify inputs for which the model is less confident and might be dealing with data not similar to the training set.

2.1.5 MLS

Minimum Logit Score (MLS) is another method for assessing model confidence, particularly useful in the context of anomaly or out-of-distribution detection. In neural networks, logits are the raw output values (before applying the softmax function) for each class. MLS is defined as the minimum logit value across all classes for a given input. Low minimum logit scores can indicate inputs that are outliers or not well-represented in the training data, thus helping in identifying uncertain predictions.

2.1.6 Distance Based

Distance-based methods are a subset of machine learning algorithms that rely on measuring distances or similarities between data points to make predictions. These methods assume that similar data points should belong to the same class and utilize a distance metric, such as Euclidean distance, cosine similarity, or Manhattan distance, to quantify the similarity between instances.

2.1.7 Cross Entropy (L2 Norm)

Cross-entropy is a loss function commonly used in classification problems to measure the performance of a model whose output

Table 1. Both models have been trained with CE loss

DGCNN						
	SR1		SR2		AVG	
Method	AUROC	FP95%	AUROC	FP95%	AUROC	FP95%
MSP	72.36	88.87	60.53	92.01	66.45	90.44
MLS	70.09	88.62	63.60	89.87	66.85	89.25
Entropy	72.17	90.21	61.05	90.01	66.61	90.11
CE(L2)	68.22	84.89	59.80	94.81	64.01	89.85
Cosine	70.17	87.65	64.46	92.25	67.32	89.95
PointNet++						
	SR1		SR2		AVG	
Method	AUROC	FP95%	AUROC	FP95%	AUROC	FP95%
MSP	82.31	79.82	72.35	85.63	77.33	82.73
MLS	83.11	71.38	70.64	85.30	76.88	78.34
Entropy	82.56	76.64	72.59	83.30	77.58	79.97
CE(L2)	79.90	84.83	75.88	77.97	77.89	81.40
Cosine	77.59	88.44	76.00	81.76	76.80	85.10

is a probability distribution. It quantifies the difference between two probability distributions: the true labels and the predicted probabilities. The L2 variant of cross-entropy combines this measure with L2 regularization, which adds a penalty proportional to the square of the magnitude of the model parameters. This combination helps prevent overfitting by encouraging the model to keep the weights small, thereby enhancing generalization.

2.1.8 Cosine Similarity on the Hypersphere

Cosine similarity is a measure used to evaluate the similarity between two non-zero vectors in an inner product space. On the hypersphere, this measure is particularly useful in high-dimensional spaces. Cosine similarity is defined as the cosine of the angle between two vectors, calculated as the dot product of the vectors divided by the product of their magnitudes. On the hypersphere, all points are normalized to unit length, simplifying the calculation as the magnitudes are unity. This metric is often used in machine learning for tasks like clustering and similarity-based retrieval.

3. Semantic Novelty Detection Baselines

We replicated 3DOS results in the Synthetic to Real scenario, both on DGCNN and PointNet++. We trained both our model with two different loss functions: Cross Entropy L^2 and Cosine Similarity. We also created 3 different subsets of our datasets: SR1, SR2 and what we called OOD2. We trained each model on ModelNet two times, with SR1 and SR2, but not with OOD2, using it as a control group to better underline the impact of the difficulty of the learning context to our task. We then tested our four models with a test sample, from ScanObjectNN, drawn from the same subset(ID), with one drawn from the other one (OOD1) and with the control one (OOD2). **Table 1** illustrates the results of our models, when trained with the Cross Entropy loss, that has proven to perform better with our metrics.

As we can see from the table, the MLS outperforms the MSP baseline results both in terms of AUROC and FPR95 as we expected besides the fact that PointNet++ backbone seems to be more robust to the domain shift than DGCNN as we can notice

Table 2. Accuracy vs AUROC for the same models

Method	Accuracy	AUROC	Backbone
MSP	71.5	66.45	DGCNN
	80.21	77.33	PointNet++
MLS	71.81	66.85	DGCNN
	80.68	76.88	PointNet++
Entropy	71.63	66.61	DGCNN
	81.2	77.58	PointNet++
CE(L2)	72.41	64.01	DGCNN
	80.56	77.89	PointNet++
Cosine	72.22	67.32	DGCNN
	81.51	76.8	PointNet++

a clear degradation in the performance.

On the other hand, The results of distance-based methods depend particularly on the backbone chosen. For instance, Cosine performs particularly well on PointNet++, but suffers a lot when we switch to DGCNN, which could suggest that DGCNN prototypes trained on synthetic data not efficiently represent the real-world test distribution.

We notice almost the same thing for CE (L^2), confirming the robustness of PointNet++ to the domain shift. by the same token, we can perform a further performance comparison in terms of Accuracy and AUROC as we can see in **Table 2**. As we have seen above, PointNet++ clearly outperforms DGCNN in terms of both accuracy and AUROC by almost a constant rate regardless of the chosen method.

4. Failure-Case Processing

4.1. Threshold Setting

To inspect the reasons behind the failure of the model in distinguishing between OOD and ID samples, our main approach consists in performing different binary classifications and quantifying the amount of misclassified samples by monitoring their distribution. In particular, The latter task is done by comparing 5 different threshold-based methods [12], taking into account the different confidences and the fact that the values above the threshold are classified as ID and all the values below as OOD, and selecting the optimal cutoff based the maximization of the different criteria below:

F1-score:

$$F1 = 2 \times \frac{\text{precision} \times \text{recall}}{\text{precision} + \text{recall}}$$

Youden Index (J):

$$J = \text{sensitivity} + \text{specificity} - 1$$

The Closest to (0,1) Criteria (ER):

$$ER = (1 - \text{sensitivity})^2 + (1 - \text{specificity})^2$$

Concordance Probability:

$$CZ = \text{sensitivity} \times \text{specificity}$$

Index of Union (IU):

$$IU = |\text{sensitivity} - AUC| + |\text{specificity} - AUC|$$

Table 3. Results on the Synthetic to Real Benchmark track SR1 using MSP only

SR1		ID				
MSP	Predicted	Chair	Door	Shelf	Sink	Sofa
	Actual					
ID	Chair	96.00%	0.00%	3.54%	0.50%	0.00%
	Door	0.00%	99.00%	0.00%	0.55%	0.00%
	Shelf	4.12%	1.87%	89.00%	1.87%	3.37%
	Sink	18.64%	0.00%	0.85%	54.00%	26.27%
	Sofa	44.09%	0.00%	0.00%	8.66%	47.00%
OOD	Bed	37.04%	0.00%	7.41%	24.44%	31.11%
	Toilet	78.05%	0.00%	2.44%	19.51%	0.00%
	Display	10.50%	25.97%	61.33%	1.66%	0.55%
	Desk+Table	36.67%	0.26%	35.38%	21.54%	6.15%

Table 4. Toilet vs Chair

Method	Class	Prediction	Times	Total
MSP	Toilet	Chair	64	82
MLS	Toilet	Chair	61	82
Cosine	Toilet	Chair	47	82
CE(L2)	Toilet	Chair	54	82

We point out that our failure-case processing has been conducted using **MSP**, **MLS**, **CE(L^2)** and **Cosine** methods on top of two different backbones, with both training datasets split (SR1 and SR2), exploiting the different thresholding methods mentioned above.

4.2. Failure-Case Identification

A straightforward look at the two table **Table 3**, which will be the subject of our analysis throughout the next subsection, shows different interesting cases for further analysis and processing. To be more precise, we decided to focus on two of the most frequent failure cases reported in **Table 4** and **Table 5**. For our discussion in this subsection, we will focus only on comparing the two classes Chair and Toilet whereas the comparison between Door and Display will be incorporated during our discussion in the next subsection.

Figure 3

Figure 4

Table 5. Display vs Door

Method	Class	Prediction	Times	Total
MSP	Display	Door	95	181
MLS	Display	Door	47	181
Cosine	Display	Door	41	181
CE(L2)	Display	Door	91	181

Using MLS, we can see that the model seems more confident that Toilet and Chair are the same as this happens 64 out of 82 times with a tiny better performance than MSP. We also notice that Cosine and $CE(L^2)$ seem more robust to this confusion. To better monitor the behavior of the separating process between Chair and the other categories, on one hand, and Chair and Toilet, on the other, we trained a binary classifier with different label encodings, applied with different thresholding methods using in particular and focusing only on the results obtained with MSP method. The same thing could be done with the other methods. The results are shown in **Figure 5**

Figure 5

Although these thresholding methods follow different dynamics based on the value of the threshold, we can see that the best common possible value for the threshold is **0.98953** corresponding to the maximum value of **Youden index (J)** given by **0.3135** as shown in **Figure 6** below

Figure 6

With the aforementioned threshold which corresponds to the confusion matrix in **Figure 7**, we can see that the overall performance of the model is not affected by much as the model succeeds in detecting most of ID samples but fails in the classification of **45%** of the OOD samples. This result was expected as the main problem for the Chair is the Toilet class but the latter's effect becomes almost negligible when we normalize with respect to the large size of the dataset. Repeating the same process as above but focusing only on Chair vs Toilet, the optimal cutoff turns out to be **0.999964** (almost 1), larger than the previously obtained one, and corresponding to a **Youden index (J)** of **0.09883**, smaller than the previous **0.3135**. Again, this was expected as we have removed the effect of the size brought by the consideration of the whole dataset. With this threshold, we can see through its corresponding confusion matrix, in **figure 8**, that despite the model succeeds in detecting all the ID samples, there is a drastic decrease in the overall performance as the model fails in the detection of **88%** of the OOD samples.

4.3. Failure-Case Analysis

Before delving into the error analysis, our idea was to gain some insight into the inter/intra-statistical dependence between the different point clouds. As a first step, we conducted a nonparametric Test for Equality of multivariate densities of the different shapes as proposed in [6]. We started by fitting two copulas to the different point clouds then compared the two multivariate empirical distributions to check for multivariate dependence. The results show that the p-value of the test is too small (far less than the standard 5%), we concluded that the two multivariate densities are statistically different in terms of the dependences seen as a whole.

99 Bootstrap Replications

Test Statistic 'Srho': **0.01629915** P-Value: **< 2.22e-16 *****

Signif. codes: **0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1**
Null of equality is rejected at the 0.1% level

Table 6. Statistical Test results

With the evidence of inter-independence among the different

shapes, we decided to perform some experiments to analyze the performance of OOD detection and Open-Set methods on the Synthetic and synthetic to real Benchmarks. In particular, we are interested in the error analysis. We report the results, found with MSP on SR1 only, in **Table 3**. The results related to the other methods are omitted to avoid cumbersome but can be found in the same GitHub repository. We can see that in general, In-Distribution data are successfully captured. When it comes to Out-of-Distribution Data, all the methods seem to follow almost the same pattern. For example, chair, Toilet are interchangeable and the same thing holds for Door, Shelf and Display. For the sake of curiosity, we started the analysis of intra-dependencies between the different dimensions, and we have noticed, in particular, that interchangeable shapes like Chair, Toilet do have some intra-pairwise dependencies which can be shown in **Figure 7** below

Figure 7. Door (left) vs Display (right)

Instead, we noticed also that in the case of door, shelf and display, there are no particular associations between the dimensions and the points seem to be randomly distributed as shown in **Figure 8**

To provide a statistical proof, we took, in particular, the multivariate empirical copulas of both Chair and Toilet then we conducted a **Kolmogorov–Smirnov test** aiming at capturing eventual dimension-wise dependence. The results of this test are the following:

- P-value for dimension 1: 0.9993
- P-value for dimension 2: 0.0000
- P-value for dimension 3: 1.0000

We notice that the p-values along dimensions 1 and 3 are less than the usual significance level of 5%, we conclude that the empirical copulas, underlying Chair and Toilet are the same along these two dimensions and different along dimension 2. So far, we know that the two shapes, not only have a pairwise dependence inside of each but also the underlying empirical copulas behave the same along two of the dimensions. By the same mathematical token, we decided to look for more similarity

Figure 8. Door (left) vs Display (right)

key points, by checking the distributional properties. In fact, by applying Principal Component Analysis to both shapes, we can see that the amounts of variation captured by the respective PCs are almost the same as shown in **Figure 9** below:

Figure 9. PCA on Chair(left) vs Toilet (right)

PCA and the inter-pairwise dependence shown earlier suggest, in particular, that along the different dimensions, there are some main common patterns between the two shapes that push the model to be uncertain about the choice to make. To verify this, we performed a continuous version of the Correspondence Analysis. In particular, We looked for correspondences between points using the Iterative Closest Point (ICP) [7] algorithm which operates by, first, aligning the two point clouds, then uses a tree-based procedure to find the nearest neighbors between points in the aligned point clouds. The results of this experiment are shown in **Figure 10**. As we have suspected, the plot shows clearly some important common patterns between the underlying two shapes which confirms our hypothesis. Further analysis could be performed, in particular from geometric and topological perspectives to gain a deep understanding of the two shapes and extrapolate valuable insights. It's worth mentioning that a similar analysis could be done for any pair of failure cases. To give another flavour to our analysis i.e. from the perspective of the evaluated methods on top of the same backbone, we decided to apply Grad-CAM (Gradient-weighted Class Activation Mapping) [10] algorithm. The latter allows us to get a sense of what regions of the image the model and the convolutional neural network are looking at to make a prediction. This is done by inspecting which individual regions

Figure 10. Correspondence Points between Chair and Toilet

have the highest-class activation and determining which parts of it have the highest values. We can also inspect the directions and the magnitude of the gradients to see which regions of the images that have been processed are now accounting for the most gradients and most updates in the neural network to get a deeper understanding of what it looks like in the original input space. In our case, the purpose of using Grad-Cam was to get a sense and compare MSP and MLS methods. In **Figure 11**, we have two superimposed visualizations, for both chair and Toilet, in which we see the direction of most of the gradients and we can easily notice, for both classes, that the area covered by the gradients when we use MLS (left) is slightly wider than the one covered when we use MSP which, basically, confirms why MLS is doing better than MSP as it allows for a better understanding and accordingly a better recognition of the underlying shape:

Figure 11. Grad-CAM on Chair and Toilet with MLS (left) and MSP (right)

The two figures above, besides emphasizing the difference between MLS and MSP, show why Toilet is mostly seen as a Chair since the model looks exactly where the two shapes are

Table 7. DGCNN backbone. Result on corrupted images.

Method	SR1(Easy)		SR2(Hard)	
	AUROC	FPR95	AUROC	FPR95
MSP	74.53	85.38	56.98	91.64
MLS	76.14	81.65	58.45	92.15
Entropy	75.21	81.71	61.70	90.63
CL(12)	67.29	82.87	70.51	76.12
Cosine	75.53	80.86	62.72	94.29

similar in terms of the dependence and the analysis performed earlier.

Taking into account that we’re using PointNet as a backbone for our analysis (for the sake of both: speeding up the process and computational limitations), the reason why the methods seem on par in terms of failing can be explained by the fact that all the components of the 3D point clouds are normalized to have the same magnitude which explains why Cosine and L2 distance capture pretty much the same thing. Furthermore, the failure could be exacerbated due to many reasons such as the PointNet’s feature extractor that ignores geometrical structure information and potential correlation between the local regions, ignoring the relationship between the local region and the global shape besides the presence of noise and distributional shift when we move from synthetic to real-world data.

5. Methods Performance Enhancement

During this whole section, we always conducted our analysis and experiments using models trained on synthetic data. This turns out in line with some of the poor performances that we came across earlier since the switch from synthetic to reality has a strong effect on the detection mechanism. The latter can be explained by many factors like the fact that synthetic data can be generated using algorithms and simulations, 3D models or CAD data and accordingly, they are expected to be typically cleaner and less noisy providing control over the density and the distribution of points and therefore their geometry. This may not exist in reality as real-world data suffer from a lot of noise and imperfections like partiality, occlusion and background points. To reduce the discrepancy generated by the domain shift, a possible solution consists in simulating the real-world conditions at training time. In particular, we performed different experiments including the Occlusion and LIDAR augmentations from [7] using MSP, MLS baselines, $CE(L^2)$, Entropy and Cosine methods on top of the DGCNN backbone. The results are reported in **Table 7** and **Table 8**

Table 7 shows how using corrupted images in the training phase improves the performance of our architecture, especially when trained on SR1. By using a training set that is more “realistic”, more close to the test one, the domain shift results in having less impact: our backbone now results less over-fitted on synthetic regular objects and can generalize more.

Table 8. DGCNN backbone. Result comparison between regular and corrupted images.

Method	Corrupted vs Standard			
	SR1		SR1	
	AUROC	FPR95	AUROC	FPR95
MSP	1.37	-3.18	0.82	-1.13
MLS	7.51	-5.13	0.97	-1.14
ENTROPY	2.34	-7.40	5.4283	-1.42
CE_L2	2.90	-4.71	11.52	-16.22
COSINE	9.07	-13.76	2.88	4.04

6. Leveraging a Pretrained Model for OOD

We then investigate the incorporation of large-scale pre-trained models to improve the task of Point Cloud semantic novelty detection. Rather than training a model specifically on the ID data, the adopted method was instead to retrieve latent features of both ID and test data from a general point cloud feature encoder. The backbone used was a pretrained Transformer network based on PointBERT [16], coming from an OpenShape [5] checkpoint.

6.1. Method

To perform the OOD detection task, we first feed the encoder with ID point clouds to extract and save encodings of in-distribution data. Then, every test input point cloud is also transformed into a latent vector, and for each one, a prediction label and an abnormality score are assigned based on the $CE(L^2)$ difference with the nearest ID point cloud latent representation computed before.

6.2. Results

We then decided to compare the results obtained from this network with those derived from PointNet++. Although the models achieve similar results regarding classification accuracy (Table 10), it is noted that for the OOD detection task, the model trained specifically for this purpose performs better than the pre-trained one (Table 9). Delving deeper into our analysis, a primary cause of this difference can be found in the different number of points sampled during the training phase by the two models. PointNet++ receives 1024 points, while PointBERT 10000. However, during the test phase, the point clouds obtained from ScanObject are composed of 2048 points, which could explain the difficulties faced by PointBERT. We also believe that this discrepancy is related to the latent feature space in which the two models operate and the metric used for comparison: the latent features emitted by PointBERT reside in a 1280-dimensional space \mathbb{R}^{1280} , while those obtained from PointNet++ reside in a 256-dimensional space \mathbb{R}^{256} causing the distances observed in the case of PointBERT from the nearest neighbors to be much higher compared to PointNet++ ones, resulting in a compression of the confidences related to the predictions, obtained as the inverse of these distances, making it very difficult to find a threshold that distinctly separates a confident prediction from an uncertain one (Table 12). Taking inspiration from [1], where it has been shown that the ratio of the

Table 9. OOD detection using different models

Method	SR1		SR2	
	AUROC \uparrow	FPR95 \downarrow	AUROC \uparrow	FPR95 \downarrow
PointBERT	64.91%	87.83%	66.89%	88.34%
PointNet++	77.73%	84.16%	75.84%	81.64%

Table 10. Accuracy based Comparison between PointNet++ and PointBERT

METHOD	ACCURACY \uparrow	
	SR1	SR2
PointBERT	79.2%	77.28%
PointNet++	76.97%	80.96%

Table 11. PointBERT Performance as a function of k

L ^k	ACC \uparrow	AUROC \uparrow	FPR95 \downarrow
2	79.2%	64.91%	87.83%
0.1	81.39%	65.07%	86.67%

Table 12. Comparison between PointNet++ and PointBERT in terms of the prediction confidence wrt Class Shelf

PointNet++			
Class	Prediction	Avg_Conf	Avg_Dist
shelf	shelf	0.48	2.07
shelf	chair	0.24	4.14
shelf	sofa	0.32	3.14
shelf	door	0.19	5.15
shelf	sink	0.14	7.19
PointBERT			
Class	Prediction	Avg_Conf	Avg_Dist
shelf	shelf	0.00152	655.881
shelf	door	0.00137	729.923
shelf	sofa	0.00145	689.362
shelf	sink	0.00143	697.022

distances of the nearest and farthest neighbors to a given target in high-dimensional space is almost 1, we investigated the use of a distance calculated on a norm with $k < 2$, with results obtained for $k=0.1$ in (Table 11). Although a certain improvement is achieved, our experiments lead us to believe that a metric based on Euclidean distance is not optimal for the OOD detection task when the features reside in a very high-dimensional space.

7. A Real World Application Proposal for 3D Semantic Novelty Detection

"Automatic Fetal Ultrasound Standard Plane Detection Using Knowledge Transferred Recurrent Neural Networks" by

Songyuan Tang et al [4],(2017), discusses the usage of a RNN to handle a sequence of 2D ultrasound data to measure different features of fetu.

Today 3D ultrasound representations are accurate enough to be trustworthy, so what we propose it to handle the same task with a 3D classifier, such that the RNN won't be needed anymore. We already have 3D voxel based techniques to handle even more complex tasks as medYOLO [11] for semantic segmentation.

Furthermore, a 3D semantic novelty detection module could be used for early anomaly detection in fetu, eventually leading to more detailed optional tests. The capability of finding non explicitly prescribed irregularities may both help refining the screening process itself and allow doctors to take a more informed decision prescribing further tests to patients.

The problem of incomplete, cluttered and noisy 3D scans is usually handled from multiple different angles. Apart from well known data preprocessing techniques, contrastive learning may be used to remove a certain degree of unwanted information, present in raw data but not to be considered for the specific task.

It is important to underline that some preprocessing operations might bias novelty detection, especially if handled through OOD detection: the more points I miss, the most novelty detection is invalidated because it is all about finding unexpected patterns in the observations wrt the training population.

The backbone also plays an important role. For example, PointNet++ is far more robust on pointclouds with different densities and it is also more resilient to noise because it searches for regularities not only at a small scale but also at a higher one.

8. Conclusion

Throughout the analysis and experiments conducted in this study, we have thoroughly examined the problem of out-of-distribution (OOD) detection for 3D point clouds, highlighting its critical importance in ensuring the reliability and robustness for real-world safety-demanding applications. In our investigation, we covered a wide range of methods assessed on top of different backbones leveraging the inspiration taken from 3DOS [2]. Key insights from our failure case analysis, using some statistical and feature matching approaches, include the importance of multivariate dependence modeling in demystifying some of the aspects behind the errors made by the different evaluated models. Our experiments also demonstrate that incorporating corrupted images during the training process, to mimic real-world data and expose the models to a wider variety of scenarios, enhances robustness during the testing process and is therefore essential for fostering the development of more generalizable models. Additionally, we highlighted, in particular, the vulnerability of multimodal pre-trained models to the curse of dimensionality, especially when they rely on proximity and distance-based metrics and we introduced a possible real-world application for 3D Semantic Novelty Detection.

Finally, it is worth mentioning that despite the significant strides that have been made in OOD detection, there is still room for continuous innovation to develop models that can be reliably deployed in diverse and dynamic real-world environments.

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